

Diurnal pattern of net radiation (Rn) and soil heat flux (G) (A), and air temperature (Ta) and floodwater temperature (Tw) (B) in rice at selected agroforestry sites and control, 30 Aug 1997.

magnitude of these fluctuations in Rn, observed on a short-term (second) basis, has a profound effect on crop growth (Knapp and Smith 1990). The development rate of rice is highest at

24–26 °C (Summerfield et al 1992). In this study, air and floodwater temperatures were far greater than this optimum range in the sole crop than in agroforestry (see figure).

Modified microclimates and differences in crop growth parameters can have profound effects on rice yields. The data set presented here is limited because it only indicates possible responses that could be expected under agroforestry. The data, however, suggest options for modifying the crop microclimate by using tree row spacing, orientation, and pruning as management tools in agroforestry. Hence, apart from modifying the crop microclimate by manipulating the canopy architecture through breeding programs, obtaining favorable growth parameters at the same levels of input use under agroforestry conditions can also be a viable management tool.

References

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Seeding density of rice and its effects on ratoon crop

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We studied the effect of seeding density on the main crop and on a ratoon crop in Santa Catarina State, southern Brazil, located at 28° 56' S in the summer of 1994, 1995, and 1996. The field experiments were conducted in a randomized complete block design with five treatments in 1994 and six in the other 2 years, in four replications at the same site in the 3 years. The soil at the experimental site was Cambicisol Gley. Fertilizer applications for the main crop were 90-40-60 kg NPK ha⁻¹ as urea,

triple superphosphate, and potassium chloride.

An early maturing cultivar (115 d), EPAGRI 106, was seeded with pregerminated seeds in an irrigated lowland rice field during the recommended period (15 October–15 November) at the following treatment rates (kg ha⁻¹): 130 (recommended); 130 + 25% of recommended rate (rr); 130 + 50% rr; 130 + 75% rr; and 130 + 100% rr (260 kg ha⁻¹). In the last 2 years, one more treatment with 100

kg ha⁻¹ was added. The cycle of the main crop (115 d) plus the ratoon (60 d) was 175 d. All data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the F test and linear regression, estimating the response for linear or quadratic effect whenever these effects were significant (F test, $P < 0.05$). The effect of density on yield of the main crop was not significant for any of the 3 years. For the last 2 years, the density × year interaction was not significant (see table).

Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of main crop and ratoon crop.

Treatment	Year			Av of 1995-96
	1994	1995	1996	
<i>Main crop</i>				
100 kg ha ⁻¹	–	6.7	8.3	7.5
130 kg ha ⁻¹	5.8	6.8	8.2	7.5
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 25% of rr ^a	5.3	7.1	8.3	7.7
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 50% of rr	5.3	7.0	8.3	7.7
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 75% of rr	7.5	7.3	8.1	7.7
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 100% of rr	5.5	6.9	8.3	7.6
Av	5.9	7.0	8.2	7.6
CV (%)	19.2	4.8	3.5	4.1
<i>Ratoon crop</i>				
100 kg ha ⁻¹	–	2.2	2.6	2.4
130 kg ha ⁻¹	0.9	2.4	2.6	2.5
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 25% of rr	0.8	2.6	2.6	2.6
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 50% of rr	0.6	2.4	2.5	2.5
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 75% of rr	0.6	2.4	2.6	2.5
130 kg ha ⁻¹ + 100% of rr	0.6	2.3	2.5	2.4
Av	0.7	2.4	2.6	2.5
CV (%)	11.6	9.1	6.4	7.8

^arr = recommended rates.

In all treatments, the main crop lodged because of heavy rain during grain filling, thus reducing crop yields, particularly ratoon crop yields. Thus, the 1994 ratoon crop data were not analyzed. For 1995 and 1996, neither the density × year interaction nor the main effect of density was significant for the ratoon crop (see table).

Since an increase in seeding density did not have a significant effect on ratoon grain yield or on main crop yield, it is recommended that the normal seeding density (130 kg ha⁻¹) be used. During years when lodging is a problem in the main crop, ratoon production is not recommended.

Effect of seeding time and fertilizer rate on rice ratooning

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Experiments were conducted to study the effect of (1) seeding time of the main crop on the ratoon crop, planted in observation plots, and (2) fertilizer rate on the ratoon crop in Santa Catarina State, southern Brazil, in the summer of 1994, 1995, and 1996. The soil at the experimental site was a Cambicisol Gley.

An early maturing cultivar (115 d), EPAGRI 106, was seeded in both experiments using pregerminated seeds in an irrigated lowland rice field at the recommended rate of 130 kg ha⁻¹. Observation plots (experiment 1) were seeded at three different times: early (20 September–10 October), normal (recommended, 15 October–15 November), and late (20 November–20 December), with three replications in each trial.

In experiment 2, seeding was done at the recommended time in a randomized complete block design with four replications and six fertilizer treatments.

The soil used in this experiment had a pH of 4.7; organic matter, 2.1%; P, 2.5 ppm; and K, 60 ppm. The complete cycle of the main crop (115 d) and ratoon crop (60 d) was 175 d. The six fertilizer treatments applied on the ratoon crop were fractions of that applied on the main crop, which was the recommended rate according to the soil analysis (90-40-60 of NPK). The treatments were (1) 1/2 of N, (2) 1/4 of N, (3) 1/2 of NPK, (4) 1/2 of NK, (5) 1/2 of NP, and (6) no fertilizer. All treatments were applied right after harvesting the main crop and then flooding.

In 1994, the main and ratoon crops lodged in all treatments because of heavy rain, resulting in a large yield reduction in all experiments.

For seeding time, only the early seeding date produced a good main crop and ratoon crop together (Table 1). For fertilizer rate, treatment 1 had the same results as the untreated plot (no. 6). The other treatments had statistically higher yields according to Dunnett's one-tailed T-test with *P* < 0.05 (Table 2).

Table 1. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of main crop and ratoon seeded at three different times.

Treatment	1994		1995		1996		Main crop + ratoon		
	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main	Ratoon crop	Main	Ratoon	1994	1995	1996
Early	6.4	1.5	4.9	2.1	6.3	2.0	7.9	7.0	8.3
Normal	6.3	2.1	5.7	1.5	4.1	0	8.4	7.2	4.1
Late	4.6	0	5.3	0	4.5	0	4.6	5.3	4.5